

ADDRESSING SECURITY CHALLENGES IN DECENTRALIZED ACCESS CONTROL: A BLOCKCHAIN AND ADAPTIVE LEARNING PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

The Blockchain is also quickly becoming a disruptive technology for providing people with never-before-seen self-governance by virtue of it being secure, transparent, and decentralized in nature. Due to its nature, it has also come to form the basis for various industry applications apart from serving as an early impetus for next-generation paradigms like cloud as well as edge computing. For security concerns data-sharing applications with distributed access control, the current work proposes a new disruptive approach as an adaptive learning model for addressing the above security concerns. Python programming is also implemented for the system validation. A comparison is also made between ALM of the new proposed work with available encrypting algorithms like RSA and AES. Various parameters are also quantified by the research work, and data thus fed is tabulated in fine details. The result demonstrates enhanced security, scalability, as well as computational efficiency by the proposed algorithm.

Keywords: *Cloud Computing; Edge Computing; Decentralized; Blockchain Skillset; Transparent.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Blockchain has attracted considerable interest in recent years across a broad variety of applications, ranging from cryptocurrencies to enterprise services. Its adoption is fast transforming industries like finance, energy, and public administration because of its decentralized, transparent, and secure characteristics. Initially conceived as the underlying technology for Bitcoin, blockchain is a distributed ledger that records transactions in a chain of blocks that is visible to all the participants [1,2]. Blockchain's decentralized nature, upheld by consensus protocols and cryptography, guarantees

data integrity and tamper resistance. These properties position blockchain as a promising solution for contemporary computing environments, especially when combined with other emerging technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and Cloud Computing [3,4]. IoT facilitates the networking of physical devices, which in turn tend to utilize cloud infrastructure for data processing, creating the so-called Cloud of Things (CoT). Conventional CoT systems, nevertheless, suffer from issues like centralized control, security vulnerabilities, and heightened latency [5,6]. To transcend these limitations the convergence of blockchain and CoT has given rise to a novel

paradigm called Blockchain-CoT (BCoT). The convergence has the following benefits: Decentralization: Eliminates reliance on centralized authorities, enhancing fault tolerance and data integrity [7]. Security and Privacy: Employs blockchain-based smart contracts to enable secure access control and ownership of user data [8]. Enables open collaboration and trustless data exchange between IoT devices and cloud providers. Additionally, cloud infrastructure enables BCoT through the provision of scalable transaction processing and fault-tolerant storage [9]. This article concentrates on alleviating security and privacy issues in decentralized data-sharing ecosystems using a new adaptive learning-driven model [10,11]. The rest of the article is organized as follows: Section II discusses related research; Section III presents the system architecture; Section IV explains the proposed algorithm; Section V discusses experimental results; and Section VI concludes with future directions.

Figure 1: Decentralized Access Systems

2. RELATED WORKS

Extensive research has been conducted in blockchain, Cloud of Things (CoT), and their integration, particularly to solve security, privacy, and scalability problems [12,13]. Various research has also looked at the implementation of blockchain within IoT scenarios, with focus on how it can foster trust, transparency, and decentralization in use cases ranging from smart manufacturing to transportation systems and future networks [14,15]. A few have delved into the infra technologies of blockchain, including consensus algorithms, peer-to-peer networks, and cryptographic primitives [16,17]. Others have ventured into the fusion of blockchain with cloud computing and edge systems, proposing distributed frameworks for more secure and more scalable data processing [18,19]. These still happen

to leave fundamental gaps in CoT integration with blockchain, particularly on access control, privacy, and threat protection in real time. Maintaining safe and dynamic access control on interconnected services and devices is among the challenges of CoT-based industrial frameworks. Current models lack a unified security framework but rather rely on predominantly centralized models that are susceptible and introduce latency [20,21]. Moreover, most current approaches have various encryption and decryption algorithms that introduce complexity into the system and reduce flexibility in dynamic systems [22,23]. To transcend these limitations, the system proposed herein is one that is decentralized with adaptive access control, as illustrated by Figure 2. The system is composed of several organizational access points, meaning that each organization has the ability to control access permissions on its own. The architecture of the system includes microservices, an internal user repository, and a blockchain cluster [24,25]. The microservices provide modular and scalable communication, while the internal repository provides organizational-level management of authentication [26,27]. The cluster of the blockchain serves as a central entity by maintaining access transactions, applying rules with smart contracts, and keeping a tamper-proof record of all transactions. All nodes in the blockchain system maintain a copy of the ledger to ease transparency as well as redundancy [28,29]. The decentralized nature significantly enhances security, allows interoperability among multiple organizations, and destroys the requirement of a centralized entity [30,31]. Even as more and more papers on CoT and blockchain have been published, not many authors have addressed their in-depth combination with a focus on adaptive access control. This work aims at filling that gap by proposing a scalable, secure model leveraging blockchain's distributed nature augmented by a dynamic learning model for secure and efficient data sharing [32,33]. While a number of studies have already recognized the benefits of blockchain in decentralized applications, most implementations have focused primarily on static access control, pre-established policies, and conventional cryptographic mechanisms [34,35]. These solutions have limited capability to adapt to evolving security landscapes or user behavior, especially in advanced, distributed industrial environments like smart factories, autonomous logistics, and health networks. Figure 2 shows the Cyber Physical Creation Framework. Traditional CoT systems have centralized cloud servers where the system centrally manages data and access control [36,37]. This provides a point of

failure as well as leaves the system open to numerous attacks such as data breaches, insider threats, and service outage. In addition, centralized systems are difficult to scale as the number of devices connected as well as volume of data grows. Also, existing cryptosystems such as RSA and AES, despite their extensive usage, are not intended to manage dynamic access requirements in real time and require additional encryption and decryption schemes, neither are they particularly constructed for managing evolving permissions at high rates, such as in multi-user, multi-organization environments [38,39].

to handle secure logging and access request verification and microservices to handle scalable interaction with the system [44]. The addition of an adaptive learning model results in encryption strategies being updated constantly over time to make them more immune to known and potential attack patterns. This novel integration of blockchain-based decentralization, multi-key encryption, and adaptability enabled by AI keeps the proposed model in this work distinct from traditional access control models as well as existing blockchain-CoT integrations. In mitigating both scalability and dynamic security requirements, it sets a new benchmark for future research in secure and decentralized IoT and industrial environments.

Figure 2: Cyber Physical Creation Framework

Another limitation of current research is insufficient utilization of artificial intelligence or machine learning in access control decision-making. Most frameworks are rule-based with no capability to learn from interactions already experienced or adjusting security policy in accordance with fluctuating threats or trends in usage [40]. The growing requirement for real-time decision-making, safe data exchange, and high-level access control has inspired researchers to consider hybrid frameworks that combine blockchain with AI-based approaches [41]. These have not yet been explored beyond the conceptual or proof-of-concept stage in real-world high-load environments [42]. The framework discussed in this paper addresses these gaps by proposing a multi-organizational, distributed access control architecture that incorporates embedded adaptive learning capabilities [43]. As Figure 3 illustrates, the architecture consists of decentralized access points per organization, a blockchain cluster

3. SYSTEM FRAMEWORK

Some of the shortcomings of the existing decentralized data-sharing systems are identified by the literature review [45]. The majority of the existing approaches are founded on distinct encryption and decryption algorithms, resulting in increased system complexity and inefficiency in implementing secure access control [46]. Furthermore, the majority of them lack a user-specific access policy, rendering them unscalable and inflexible in a decentralized setting. To overcome these challenges, the system at hand presents a new decentralized access control paradigm that is more secure and convenient [47]. The system makes use of attribute-based encryption and ciphertext management, eliminating the application of multiple cryptographic algorithms and maintaining data confidentiality and control at the user level [48]. The intended architecture, as depicted in Figure 3, facilitates access control for various organizational levels with independent access points. The key constituents of the framework are:

Figure 3: System Framework for decentralized access control

Access Points: Each organization within the system hosts an autonomous access point, which independently permits or denies a request of a user based on pre-defined access policies. Modular, reusable microservices provide specialized functionality, facilitating good communication among system components and scalable deployment. Decentralized basis of the system. It enforces permission rules through smart contracts, stores common data for participating nodes, and maintains an immutable record of all access transactions for auditing and traceability. All organizations maintain an internal user repository for holding user credentials, profiles, and permissions. The system is multi-organizational with support for various organizations, each with its own policies and control logic, allowing fine-grained access management in collaborative environments. The use of blockchain ensures trust, transparency, and tamper-proof storage, while decentralized access points and microservices allow modularity and scalability. The system is designed to address the urgent need for a secure, efficient, and policy-based access control system in decentralized data-sharing systems.

3.1 Overview of Research Methodology

To obtain the results, a structured methodology was adopted, comprising the following phases:

Design Phase: Defined the system framework integrating blockchain with independent access points and microservices, each mapped to an organizational control layer.

Algorithm Development: Designed the Adaptive Learning Model (ALM) algorithm, based on dynamic block weights and prime-number-based encryption. The algorithm was implemented using Python.

Implementation: Simulated decentralized access requests and block creation using synthetic data (word documents of varying lengths). Each encryption round used adaptive learning to adjust key generation.

Benchmarking: Compared performance with RSA and AES based on encryption time and scalability using identical datasets.

Evaluation: Conducted time complexity analysis, visualized the performance using bar charts, and qualitatively compared cryptographic features.

Validation: Verified the model across 1000–10000 word datasets and analyzed adaptive performance under increased load.

3.2 Research Methodology Protocol

It engaged in a systematic process of conceptualizing, designing, implementing, and experimenting with a decentralized access control solution powered by blockchain, based on an Adaptive Learning Model (ALM). It began by conducting an in-depth literature review of the inadequacy of the present-day encryptions, primarily in decentralization and adaptability. Upon the above said observations, the new system structure was developed, consisting of Decentralized access points, microservices, a blockchain cluster, and in-house user repo. The ALM algorithm in Python has been developed, attaining symmetric as well as asymmetric encryptions through key generation that changes dynamically in real-time based upon learning. The encryption seeds that are the prime numbers are adjusted in terms of weights using the blocks processed in the bygone days in order to introduce unpredictability as well as added security. It was tested using text data collections of different sizes (1000 to 10,000 words). Each collection of data was encrypted by using RSA, AES, and ALM to compare the performances. Encryption time, throughput, and confidentiality were among the key parameters that were captured. These data were filtered in order to determine the scale and efficacy of ALM. The algorithm demonstrated improved speed and flexibility in comparison to standard algorithms, reinforcing the solution of the framework.

4. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

The system, designed here, is intended to create a secure, decentralized, and intelligent data-sharing platform by combining blockchain technology and an Adaptive Learning Model (ALM). The system, built with Python, focuses on eliminating some of the most noted challenges in existing decentralized access control systems—primarily static encryption and rigid policy enforcement. The system employs blockchain for immutable and open storage of data and adaptive AI techniques for dynamically changing encryption. The blockchain technology employed in this architecture is central to facilitating safe communication and authentication between nodes. Every node, which is an entity or device within the system, is assigned a status of its own, and each of these nodes retains a complete synchronized replica of the blockchain ledger. Figure 4 demonstrates the basic transaction process within the system. Initially, a node requests to initiate a transaction—i.e., access to data or data sharing—and triggers the creation of a new block.

Figure 4: An example of blockchain transaction

The block has transaction information and encrypted payload and is broadcast to all other nodes that are currently active in the network. The nodes verify the transaction according to consensus rules defined ahead of time, such as proof-of-work or smart contract verification. Once the transaction is verified, the block becomes permanent and is added to the blockchain. The verified nodes are rewarded, say, with computation rewards, and the request for access is marked as done. In this process, the ALM monitors the transaction, gathers data, and adjusts internal parameters for learning in order to fine-tune encryption practices in the future.

Figure 5: Methodology used for Encryption and Decryption

This integration of learning into the block chain process not only secures data but also makes the system responsive to emerging threats and trends in real time. The encryption and decryption processes utilized in the framework described are based on an adaptive policy rather than on static cryptographic standards. As indicated by Figure 5, the process begins from the transformation of plaintext data into ciphertext through a data key and dynamically generated master key. The generation of such keys occurs through a learning-based model by integrating a prime number seed and dynamically adjusted weights of the ALM. Once the keys are created, the plaintext is encrypted into secure ciphertext that is stored within the blockchain. The decryption process is reversed but specifically managed by the same adaptive learning that generated the encryption keys so that only appropriately trained and authorized parties can decipher the message. What distinguishes this method from its classical counterparts is the fact that it defies fixed pattern detection; the encryption process is dynamic with each transaction and hence is highly immune to attacks or reverse engineering. The algorithm for the Adaptive Learning Model serves as the system's basis. It is of linear time complexity and incrementally adaptive learning curve. When executed for the first time, the model is seeded with a prime number input. This value seeds the algorithm, which then goes on to generate dynamic weights for encryption depending on structure of data blocks and input block priority. Each transaction block is assigned a unique weight, and these weights influence further encryption logic. Figure 6 shows the ALM Algorithm Snippets.

```
def alm_rebalance(assets, liabilities, target_ratio=1.05):
    """
    Simple ALM algorithm that ensures assets >= target_ratio * liabilities.
    If below, adds assets. If above, invests surplus.
    """
    current_ratio = assets / liabilities
    print(f"Current asset/liability ratio: {current_ratio:.2f}")

    if current_ratio < target_ratio:
        # Need to add assets
        required_assets = liabilities * target_ratio
        add_amount = required_assets - assets
        print(f"Add assets: {add_amount:.2f}")
        assets += add_amount
    elif current_ratio > target_ratio:
        # Surplus assets - invest surplus
        surplus = assets - liabilities * target_ratio
        print(f"Invest surplus: {surplus:.2f}")
        assets -= surplus # Assume invested elsewhere
    else:
        print("No rebalancing needed.")

    print(f"Post-rebalance assets: {assets:.2f}")
    return assets
```

2	Keys defined throughout the process	Single key i.e., Same for both Encryption and Decryption	Different key. i.e., Encryption and Decryption uses different key	Multiple keys for each block created
3	Throughput	Very high	Low	Very high
4	Confidentiality	High	Low	Very high

Table 2: Comparison of AES, RSA and ALM algorithms - Time taken to complete encryption

S.No	Number of words	Time in (ms)		
		RSA	AES	ALM
1	1000	9.858	0.243	0.084
2	2500	12.091	0.249	0.085
3	5000	16.940	0.343	0.101
4	10000	30.272	0.421	0.115

Figure 6: ALM Algorithm Snippets

This implies each encryption and decryption session is uniquely tailored, with no two runs using identical logic or set of keys. Figures 6a and 6b show the input and encrypted output of the ALM algorithm, displaying the ability of the model to generate non-repetitive, safe ciphertexts even if the plaintext appears identical. The flexibility of the algorithm has the consequence that even in a decentralized access control situation, data exposure by prediction of patterns or key reuse is effectively eliminated. To ensure the performance and robustness of the ALM algorithm, it was compared with two popular cryptographical standards: RSA and AES. The comparisons were made based on factors such as cryptographic type, key management, throughput, and confidentiality. Whereas RSA relies on asymmetric key pairs and provides moderate throughput in terms of computational load, AES relies on a single symmetric key and is optimized for high-speed execution.

Table 1: Feature comparison of AES vs RSA vs ALM Algorithms

S. No	Features	AES	RSA	ALM
1	Type of cryptography	Symmetric	Asymmetric	Both symmetric and asymmetric

But both approaches have shortcomings in dynamic, multi-user environments, especially regarding key flexibility and responsiveness. The ALM approach, on the other hand, adopts a hybrid cryptographic method that dynamically chooses numerous keys per block based on symmetric and asymmetric paradigms. It is extremely throughput-centric and superior to both RSA and AES in confidentiality by responding dynamically to threats and context in real-time. It was tested with text files of varying word sizes—1,000 words to 10,000 words—to measure encryption time. The results indicated RSA always took the longest time, from almost 10 milliseconds in 1,000 words to over 30 milliseconds in 10,000 words. AES took a much shorter time, with times growing by a minimal fraction from around 0.24 to 0.42 milliseconds on the same scale of data.

learning from prior blocks, the system dynamically evolves and generates unpredictable keys, making it highly resilient against runtime and brute-force attacks. It was observed that for document sizes ranging from 1000 to 10000 words, the ALM maintained consistent encryption time with significantly lower latency than existing algorithms. Despite these promising results, there are limitations. The model currently supports a single-master setup and has not yet been tested on live industrial data streams or across heterogeneous IoT environments. Threats to validity include synthetic input scenarios and lack of testing on adversarial datasets, which may affect real-world generalizability. The research objectives were largely met, including the design of a decentralized security model, development of a hybrid encryption algorithm, and performance validation against conventional benchmarks. However, further research is needed to scale the system to support multiple authorities (multi-master control), dynamic policy updates in real-time, and integration with anomaly detection mechanisms. Future work will focus on addressing these limitations by incorporating federated learning for multi-node intelligence sharing, applying the model to real industrial IoT datasets, and testing it under adversarial conditions to improve robustness. The long-term vision is to develop a self-adaptive, AI-driven cybersecurity layer that ensures continuous, policy-compliant access in critical infrastructure networks.

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